

MicroRNAs as dynamic processors: from thresholding to temporal decoding

Szischik Candela^{1,2*}, Gándara Maribel^{2*}, Ferro Elsi³, Bosia Carla^{4,5+}, Ventura Alejandra^{1,2+}

¹Universidad de Buenos Aires, Facultad de Ciencias Exactas y Naturales, Departamento de Física, Buenos Aires, Argentina.

²Instituto de Fisiología, Biología Molecular y Neurociencias (IFIBYNE UBA - CONICET), Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas Argentina, Universidad de Buenos Aires, Buenos Aires, Argentina.

³CRS4 (Center for Advanced Studies, Research and Development in Sardinia), Pula, Italy.

⁴Department of Applied Science and Technology, Politecnico di Torino, Corso Duca degli Abruzzi 24, Torino, 10129, Italy.

⁵IIGM Foundation - Italian Institute for Genomic Medicine, c/o IRCCS, SP 142 km 3,95, Candiolo, 10060 Torino, Italy

Abstract. MicroRNAs are central regulators of gene expression. Traditionally viewed as static repressors of protein output, their regulatory role is increasingly recognized as inherently dynamic. In living systems, gene regulation unfolds far from equilibrium, where signals fluctuate over time, molecular abundances vary stochastically, and cellular decisions depend on temporal context. Within this framework, microRNA-mediated regulation emerges not simply as a buffering layer, but as an active component of dynamic information processing.

In this review, we present a dynamical perspective on microRNA-mediated regulation. We first discuss how the stoichiometric nature of microRNA-target interactions gives rise to ultrasensitive and threshold-like responses, and how these nonlinear properties extend beyond steady-state repression to shape temporal and stochastic regulation. We examine how sequestration-based mechanisms can support frequency-dependent responses, selective decoding of time-varying signals, and context-dependent modulation of gene expression noise. Together, these observations support a dynamical perspective in which microRNAs contribute to the processing, filtering, and integration of regulatory information across multiple timescales.

Keywords: microRNAs, ultrasensitivity, threshold, frequency decoding, noise modulation, cell states.

*, +: Equally contributing authors

+: To whom correspondence should be written: alejvent@fbmc.fcen.uba.ar, carla.bosia@polito.it

Introduction

MicroRNAs (miRNAs) are small non-coding RNAs that post-transcriptionally regulate gene expression [1]. They act through Watson–Crick base pairing to short miRNA response elements (MREs) on target RNAs that can be either messenger RNAs (mRNAs) or other non coding RNAs such as long non-coding RNAs or circular RNAs [2–4]. When interacting with mRNAs, they typically induce either translational repression or mRNA degradation [5], effectively lowering gene expression levels. Furthermore, since each miRNA can target multiple RNAs and each RNA can be regulated by multiple miRNAs [6], the interaction is combinatorial.

MiRNAs, along with their target elements and regulatory pathways, are highly conserved across metazoans [1, 7–9]. Consistent with this, miRNAs are deeply embedded in gene regulatory networks [10], suggesting that they have been maintained by selective pressures as functionally important, system-level regulators rather than redundant components. Despite this pervasive integration, miRNAs are still commonly described as static modulators of gene expression that attenuate protein output and may impose repression thresholds [11]. While this framework has been extremely useful, it captures only part of their regulatory potential. Cellular regulation is intrinsically dynamic. Sig-

nals are transient, inputs are pulsatile, and molecular abundances fluctuate over time [12, 13]. Many biological processes that critically depend on temporal coordination, including developmental patterning, differentiation, and cell fate transitions, also involve extensive miRNA-mediated regulation [14–20]. These observations raise the possibility that miRNAs participate not only in determining expression levels, but also in shaping how regulatory information is processed over time.

At the molecular level, miRNAs act through titration and sequestration [11]. These mechanisms are inherently nonlinear and time-dependent: they may generate thresholds, ultrasensitive responses, and finite relaxation times, all of which depend on relative concentrations and kinetic parameters. As a consequence, the effect of a miRNA cannot be fully captured by steady-state repression curves alone. The same miRNA–target interaction can behave as a strong repressor, a weak modulator, or a sharp threshold depending on when—and for how long—it is observed. Time, therefore, is not a secondary variable but a defining dimension of miRNA function.

This dynamical viewpoint reshapes how miRNAs are interpreted at the systems level. Thresholds generated by titration are not simply static decision boundaries; they determine when fluctuations are amplified or buffered, when transient signals are ignored or transmitted, and when small differences in expression are converted into distinct cellular outcomes. Similarly, the same sequestration mechanisms that underlie ultrasensitivity also introduce characteristic timescales, enabling post-transcriptional circuits to respond selectively to specific temporal patterns of upstream activity. In this sense, miRNAs are poised to decode not only signal amplitude, but also signal timing.

In the following sections, we develop this perspective by first revisiting the molecular origins of ultrasensitivity and threshold-like behavior in miRNA–target interactions, and then

extending these concepts to explicitly dynamical regimes, including frequency-dependent responses and noise regulation.

Ultrasensitivity and threshold-like behavior of miRNA–target interactions

Although miRNAs target both coding and non-coding RNAs, their functional impact has been studied primarily in the context of miRNA–mRNA interactions, where repression is more easily observed. The typical interaction between a miRNA and a target mRNA can be described using a molecular titration model similar to that proposed by Buchler and Louis [21], and shown in Figure 1a. In this framework, two molecules, one of which is ‘active’, bind together to form an inactive complex: the free mRNA acts as the active molecule (R), since it is the species that can be translated into protein, and is then inactivated when it binds to the miRNA (M) (Figure 1a).

In case of strong interaction (i.e. repression strength) between R and M , such interactions may generate a threshold-linear response curve at steady-state, characterized by three distinct regulatory regimes. First, when the mRNA synthesis rate k_R is low, the amount of free M molecules is much higher than free R molecules, so R molecules are rapidly titrated and remain in complex with M ; therefore increases in the synthesis rate of R do not lead to a significant accumulation of free R . On the other side, when k_R is high, the amount of free R molecules greatly exceeds the amount of free M molecules, and so the level of free R responds approximately linearly to changes in its synthesis. Finally, when both mRNA and miRNA synthesis rates k_R and k_M are such that the levels of both free species are similar, the system operates near a threshold that determines a qualitative change in how mRNA levels respond to the same miRNA concentration (Figure 1b). It is important to clarify that what we call ‘repression strength’ is typically defined by a combination of the bind-

ing and unbinding constants k_{on} and k_{off} , as well as the complex degradation rate (γ) and the miRNA and mRNA recycling parameters (α and β) [22, 23]. These parameters affect the shape of the curve, tuning the sharpness of the threshold, while the recycling rates also determine its position along the x-axis, together with k_R and k_M . The three regimes we mention are present in any one of the numerous parameter combinations that helps determine the presence of a threshold.

An important feature of this molecular titration mechanism is that it can behave as an ultrasensitive response motif [24]. In this context, ultrasensitivity means that, within a certain region of the dose-response curve, small variations in the input produce amplified changes in the output. This property can be quantified through the logarithmic gain, which measures the local sensitivity of the output to changes in the input [21, 25, 26] (Figure 1b). Evaluating the logarithmic gain across the response curve reveals that it reaches a maximum near the threshold region, and that this maximum exceeds one—a defining condition for ultrasensitivity—(Figure 1b). What does it mean for a system to be ultrasensitive? Although this is not the main focus of this review, it is still important to briefly clarify our definition, as multiple quantitative measures of ultrasensitivity coexist in literature. Mainly, ultrasensitivity is frequently equated with all-or-nothing responses since it is particularly relevant in many biological scenarios such as irreversible cell-fate decisions, including cellular differentiation or cell cycle progression [27]. However, not all ultrasensitive responses correspond to true switches. A switch implies an effectively binary behavior, while molecular titration typically produces a sharp but continuous transition. As discussed by Gunawardena [28] commonly used ultrasensitivity measures can be deceitful since they are not able to fully discriminate between sharp thresholds and switches. In this sense, Buchler and Cross [29] theoretically show that switch-like responses can emerge

from molecular titration interactions under certain conditions. Nevertheless, in the case of a single miRNA-mRNA interaction a switching behavior is unlikely. While it can be favoured by including some external interactions or cooperativity through multiple binding sites, the response better fits the threshold linear description [30].

Therefore, while sharing some characteristics with a switch-like response, thresholds play a different role in regulatory systems. In particular, it has been described how genetically similar cell populations respond differently to certain stimuli only depending on the presence of a particular species above or below a threshold [11, 31, 32]. Numerous examples illustrate how such threshold-like behaviors contribute to functional diversity in genetic networks. An interesting example that showcases these characteristics is a research paper that proposes thresholds as the mechanism behind a bet-hedging strategy in bacterial populations that are able to respond heterogeneously to antibiotic treatments, giving rise to a subpopulation of persistent cells that can bypass the effect of the drug and therefore remain dormant during the course of the treatment [32]. In this particular case, the threshold emerges from a protein-protein interaction, where the free level of an active protein HipA determines the duration of a growth arrest period in bacteria. In the presence of a titrant molecule, HipB, a threshold appears similarly to what is shown in Figure 1b. This threshold separates the population into two different classes: below the free HipA threshold, bacteria do not experience growth arrest, which normally represents a fitness advantage, but under stressful conditions the active growth metabolism characteristics render these bacteria more susceptible to damage or death. On the other hand, the subset of bacteria above the threshold experiences a growth arrest period that, by slowing their metabolism, allows the population to endure stressful conditions and continue reproducing, albeit more slowly, even under stress.

The titration interaction produces a functional threshold: above a certain level of HipA, the system shifts to a different regime. Such mechanisms can generate threshold-like behavior and bimodality, which are precisely the features required for bet hedging.

It is important to emphasize that the study of molecular titration has largely centered on protein–protein interactions. However, there are many cases of RNA based molecular titration, with small regulatory RNAs being considered prime examples of titration molecules [33, 34]. A particularly interesting case is the one described in the review by Cohen et al. [31], where a miRNA (miR-9) is able to produce a threshold in the expression of the *Senseless* gene in *Drosophila melanogaster*, which, coupled to a feedback loop, allows a population of sensory cell precursors to properly differentiate [35]. In this case, miR-9 inhibits the expression of *Senseless* in most of the cells, with only some of them being able to cross the expression threshold and therefore avoiding spurious cell differentiation. In this scenario, the removal of miR-9 is not critical for the fly’s survival, but it does make the differentiation process less robust. Therefore, thresholds can be considered as tools of both plasticity and robustness in regulatory networks. Identifying thresholds in this system can also help understand how endogenous RNAs competing for a shared pool of miRNAs (ceRNAs) interact in a regulatory network and how noise is modulated differently when the miRNA-mRNA stoichiometry varies [22], which will be discussed in the following sections.

The shape and presence of these thresholds in the steady-state depend on many characteristics of the interaction, the most relevant being the binding constant, but also what is called the sub-optimal catalyticity of the titrant molecule (M) [21, 22, 34]. The catalyticity refers to how efficiently the titrant molecule M is recycled after interacting with its target, represented in the model depicted in Figure 1a by the parame-

ter α . This concept is thoroughly discussed in Buchler and Louis’ 2008 paper [21], in which they explain that these thresholds are more often found in systems with a high complex degradation rate, which implies a low M recycling rate (in this case, α), and thus low catalyticity (Figure 1d). In particular, when studying the catalyticity of miRNA, many things have to be taken into account. The miRNA recycling rate is considered highly heterogeneous, as the degree of complementarity between a miRNA and its target determines which regulatory pathway is engaged. When complementarity is perfect, the slicing pathway is activated, which operates at a high catalytic rate [36]. In the canonical, non-slicing pathway — where complementarity is only partial — recycling does occur, but to a limited extent [37]. Another factor that may influence the extent of miRNA recycling is miRNA specific degradation, through the activity of certain endonucleases [38–40] or the target-directed microRNA degradation (TDMD) mechanism [41], all of which are represented by the leftward arrow in the model cartoon, and by the β parameter (Fig 1a). While it is reasonable to assume that the process is not perfectly catalytic ($\alpha \neq 0$), due in part to complex dilution through cell division, steady-state thresholds are more likely to emerge when titrant recycling is inefficient (Figure 1c,d). Consequently, strong miRNA recycling would make threshold formation less likely at steady-state (Figure 1c).

However, it is important to investigate the behavior of free mRNA while far from steady-state, since although miRNA-mediated regulation might not be as rapid as previously thought [42], they have also been described to have a regulatory impact on short timescales and out of equilibrium systems [43, 44]. In this sense, it has also been shown that thresholds also emerge as a pre-stationary phenomenon [21, 22] (Figure 1c). It is particularly interesting to study these properties in a context where the expression of a target mRNA is induced into a cell in which the miRNA that targets

it is already highly expressed. In this setting, newly transcribed mRNA is initially absorbed into miRNA–mRNA complexes, so free mRNA can remain close to zero until the miRNA pool becomes transiently saturated and the effective repression threshold is crossed, after which free mRNA starts to accumulate. This could be considered a similar scenario to the experiments performed in the works by Mukherji et al. [11] and Bosia et al. [45].

Moreover, these pre-stationary thresholds are robust to highly catalytic interactions (Figure 1c). This suggests that the system has a markedly distinct behavior when considering different time windows, which points to sensitivity to timing as a potential regulatory feature. Importantly, nonlinear responses generated by molecular titration are not restricted to steady-state input-output relationships. In dynamical systems, ultrasensitivity can interact with intrinsic kinetic timescales to selectively reshape the propagation of temporal fluctuations and oscillatory inputs. This raises the possibility that the same stoichiometric principles underlying miRNA-mediated threshold behavior may also contribute to temporal signal decoding.

Ultrasensitive systems and frequency decoding

While the role of ultrasensitivity in shaping steady-state repression has been extensively studied, considerably less attention has been devoted to its potential consequences under time-varying conditions. More generally, cells often encode regulatory information not only in signal amplitude, but also in signal timing, duration, and frequency [13]. A central question is therefore whether the sequestration mechanisms underlying miRNA-mediated ultrasensitivity can also support temporal decoding.

Cellular regulation is inherently dynamic and often mediated by molecules whose activity varies over time, frequently in a pulsatile manner [46]. Information can be encoded in fea-

tures of these signals, such as pulse amplitude, duration and frequency. While constant signals primarily regulate cellular responses through amplitude modulation, pulsatile inputs introduce additional levels of modulation as the timing-sensitivity attributes may also shape the response. Although these principles have been widely studied in signaling and transcriptional regulation, their implications for post-transcriptional regulation, particularly in miRNA-mediated systems, remain comparatively unexplored.

How such temporal patterns encode information from upstream signals and how they shape gene regulatory circuits has been largely explored [47]. In particular, the dynamics of transcription factors play a major role in controlling cellular behavior [13, 48]. For instance, the extracellular signal regulated kinase (ERK) displays pulsatile dynamics that drive cell proliferation in response to cell growth factors, whereas sustained ERK activation induces cell differentiation in response to nerve growth factor [49]. Similarly, oscillatory dynamics of transcription factors including p53 and NF- κ B can differentially regulate gene expression depending on promoter affinity and nonlinear transcriptional responses [50]. These examples illustrate how distinct temporal patterns of the same molecular signal can lead to different cellular outcomes.

A major question is how such time-varying signals are decoded into specific cellular responses. Theoretical and experimental studies have identified several molecular mechanisms by which temporal features are detected and translated into distinct cellular response such as kinetic filtering, promoter-state transitions, and gene-regulatory network motifs with intrinsic timescales [13, 50–53]. In this framework, differences in mediator stability, activation and inactivation kinetics, and network topology enable selective responses to particular temporal patterns or stimulation frequencies [12].

Frequency decoding mechanisms have been identified across multiple layers of regulation.

Simple signaling modules can behave as band-pass filters under time-limited oscillatory stimulation [54], while transcriptional network motifs such as feed-forward loops can selectively respond to specific temporal input profiles [51, 55, 56]. While most studies have focused on transcriptional regulation, the role of dynamic decoding at other regulatory layers remains less understood. In this context of miRNA-target interactions, a key question is whether sequestration, beyond generating ultrasensitivity, can also enable frequency-selective responses.

Reves Szmere and colleagues [57] have established a connection between sequestration-based mechanism and frequency-dependent responses in covalent modification cycles (CMCs). When enzymes and their target proteins are expressed at comparable concentrations, sequestration becomes significant and alters system dynamics. Under these conditions, CMCs can exhibit signal termination, namely the ability to return to lower stationary values than their peak response despite continued stimulation. Under periodic inputs, this behavior gives rise to band-pass filtering, in which responses are maximal at intermediate frequencies and attenuated at both low and high frequencies. Mechanistically, the combination of sequestration and fast/slow enzyme asymmetry introduces distinct effective timescales whose interaction yields a peak response at intermediate input frequencies.

Molecular sequestration has also been explicitly exploited for the rational design of band-pass filters in simpler network motifs. In particular, Zhang et al. [58] showed that both incoherent feed-forward loops (IFFLs) and negative feedback loops (NFLs) can display band-pass filter response under periodic stimulation when operating in the fast sequestration regime. When both motifs are combined, the band pass filter properties are leveraged and can be extended to a broader parameter region, including slow sequestration. Importantly, frequency selectivity can be tuned through sequestration strength

and production/degradation rates, highlighting sequestration as a versatile mechanism for temporal signal processing. Notably, IFFL architectures are commonly observed in miRNA-mediated regulation [59–63], although the specific molecular implementation differs in detail from the abstract sequestration-based models considered by Zhang et al.

Frequency selective behavior can emerge also in transient regimes. Szischik et al. [64] theoretically showed that elementary signalling components, such as ligand receptor and CMC motifs, can exhibit transient frequency preference when responses are measured over early time windows. Although the preferred frequency may disappear at steady state, it can propagate through cascades if upstream modules are slower than downstream ones. This establishes a system-level mechanism by which cells decode stimulus frequency under physiologically relevant, time-limited conditions.

Although several connections have been established between titration mechanism and frequency decoding, relatively little attention has been devoted to unveiling the role of pulsatility in the context of post-transcriptional gene regulation [65]. Ferro and coworkers [66] addresses this gap by showing that periodic miRNA synthesis can repress targets more effectively than constant production with the same total miRNA dose, with repression optimized at specific input frequencies (Figure 2).

Repression efficiency is quantified through fold repression (FR), defined as the ratio between the time-average constitutive level of target expression and its time-average level under miRNA regulation (Figure 2d). To compare the effect induced by periodic and constant miRNA syntheses, the average fold repression achieved by both kinds of stimuli is computed over the same timespan, corresponding to the time required to reach steady state (see Figure 2a,b). Importantly, the total miRNA dose is conserved across conditions. The authors further introduce three distinct metrics to characterize frequency-

dependent responses: the advantage of periodic over constant input (A), the selectivity of the response across frequencies (S), and the preferred frequency at which repression is maximized (f^*). The metric A quantifies the repressive advantage of periodic over constant miRNA synthesis, comparing fold repression values achieved by the two kinds of input. Selectivity measures the frequency preference behavior considering the area and the height of the fold repression curve in relation to the frequency range covered. Finally, the preferred frequency (f^*) corresponds to the frequency at which FR reaches its maximum. Formal definitions can be found in [66], while a graphical representation is provided in Figure 2e.

Authors explore how different parameters in the model, representing kinetics rates and affinities, shape the frequency response. Nonlinearities, together with the interplay between distinct timescales, such as the molecular half-lives, complex formation, and processing, emerge as key determinants of frequency preference. Crucially, the optimal frequency depends on relative kinetic rates, implying that frequency modulation enables target selectivity among multiple competing RNAs, control that goes beyond sequence pairing alone. More generally, this behavior is consistent with the idea that regulatory systems can implement distinct functional programs through time-dependent modulation of their inputs, depending on kinetic and contextual constraints, rather than solely on molecular specificity [67, 68]. In this framework, frequency modulation can be viewed as a specific dynamical feature that, by interacting with intrinsic kinetic parameters, enables selective regulation across targets.

The frequency-dependent behavior is tightly linked to the ultrasensitive nature of the underlying titration mechanism. As shown in Figure 2f,g, frequency decoding capacity, quantified by advantage and selectivity, is maximized when the system operates near the ultrasensitive threshold. This behavior can be understood

from the nonlinear input–output relationship underlying miRNA-mediated repression. In the ultrasensitive regime, the steady-state response of the target mRNA to miRNA levels has a sharp transition around a threshold set by the titration balance. When the miRNA transcription rate oscillates with fixed amplitude around a mean value that lies within this region, the system repeatedly crosses both sides of the threshold. Although the input is symmetric around the mean, the output is not: the nonlinear response amplifies the repressive effect of the upcycle relative to the compensatory derepression during the downcycle.

This asymmetry is further reinforced dynamically since relaxation toward repression and derepression occurs on different timescales, as shown in Figure 2c. In the vicinity of the ultrasensitive threshold, the system exhibits markedly different equilibration times depending on the direction of the perturbation, implying that transitions across the threshold are temporally asymmetric. Consequently, even under symmetric oscillatory input, the system effectively spends unequal time in repressed and unrepressed states. As a result, the time-averaged repression under pulsatile input becomes greater than that obtained under constant input with the same mean level. By contrast, outside the ultrasensitive regime, where the response is approximately linear, oscillations around the mean produce symmetric effects that largely cancel out over time, yielding little or no advantage. Therefore, ultrasensitivity provides the mechanistic basis for translating temporal features of miRNA transcription into differential target repression.

Interestingly, frequency preference can still emerge even in the absence of steady-state ultrasensitivity for catalytic interactions. This suggests that factors beyond the steady-state input–output relationship, particularly transient dynamics, may contribute substantially to the response. Because response is evaluated over a finite time window, transient dynamics prior

to steady state introduce effective nonlinearities. Differences in relaxation times between the increasing and decreasing phases (see Figure 2c) may also play a role in the frequency response. Recent advances in time-resolved imaging techniques have provided increasing evidence that miRNA levels can exhibit oscillatory dynamics, suggesting that such mechanisms may operate under physiological conditions. In particular, systems combining relatively stable miRNAs with unstable target mRNAs may be especially suited to exploit this mechanism. Circadian expressed miRNAs, such as miR-96, miR-182, miR-219-1 and dme-miR-263a [69–71], have been reported to target unstable transcripts [72, 73], potentially placing them within this dynamic range.

Taken together, beyond their established roles as molecular switches or fine-tuners of gene expression, miRNAs may act as dynamic decoders, translating upstream temporal signals into selective post-transcriptional responses. Importantly, the same nonlinear and kinetic features that enable temporal selectivity are also expected to shape how fluctuations propagate through post-transcriptional regulatory networks, linking dynamic decoding to noise modulation and phenotypic variability.

Noise Control in miRNA Networks

MiRNA-mediated regulation shapes not only mean gene expression but also its stochastic properties, and the same nonlinear threshold mechanisms that enable temporal decoding also reshape stochastic fluctuations. Gene expression is inherently stochastic due to the discrete nature of transcription and translation [74–76]. In minimal single-cell descriptions, protein production occurs in bursts, and mean protein abundance depends on both burst frequency and burst amplitude, the latter defined as the number of proteins produced per transcriptional event [77, 78]. Importantly, the relative fluctuations of protein abundance depend not only on mean expres-

sion levels but also explicitly on burst amplitude, which is set by the ratio between protein translation and mRNA degradation rates [76–78]. This implies that regulatory mechanisms acting on this parameter can directly control expression noise independently of average protein levels.

Post-transcriptional regulation by miRNAs is therefore naturally linked to noise control [34, 79–81]. Acting downstream of transcription, miRNAs reduce translational efficiency and/or promote mRNA degradation, thereby limiting protein burst amplitude. Theoretical analyses by Osella and coworkers [82, 83] have shown that, at fixed mean expression, miRNAs can reduce noise precisely through this mechanism, providing a mechanistic basis for their role in expression robustness. This establishes a direct link between post-transcriptional ultrasensitivity and noise regulation.

In specific regulatory architectures, such control manifests as noise buffering. A pivotal example is the IFFL, in which a transcription factor regulates both a target gene and its repressive miRNA: correlations between target mRNA and miRNA levels compensate upstream fluctuations, reducing protein-level variability [60, 84]. Noise attenuation is maximal under moderate repression, consistent with miRNAs acting as fine-tuners rather than switches [82, 85]. Similar buffering effects have been predicted or observed in other circuit contexts where miRNA regulation is correlated with upstream transcriptional inputs, reinforcing the idea that ultrasensitivity can be exploited to stabilize gene expression outputs [83, 86–88].

By contrast —as discussed in the context of threshold-like behavior above— when miRNA–target regulation operates near a regime of near equimolarity, in which miRNAs and their targets are present at comparable abundances, ultrasensitivity leads to qualitatively different behavior. In this so-called titration regime, saturation of the miRNA pool introduces an effective nonlinear threshold separat-

ing strongly repressed and derepressed regimes [11]. As a consequence, small stochastic fluctuations in transcription or degradation rates can be strongly amplified, leading to a noisier target expression [22, 89], see Figure 3a-c. Near equimolarity, the ultrasensitive response of individual target genes is no longer an isolated property of single interactions [10]. Instead, multiple ultrasensitive regulatory modules become effectively coupled through the shared miRNA pool, Figure 3d. In this situation, the system enters a collective titration regime, in which the nonlinear response of each target depends not only on its own expression level, but also on the abundance and fluctuations of all other competing targets [22, 89], revealing an active role of retroactivity [90], Figure 3e.

A defining feature of this collective titration regime is the emergence of effective crosstalk among miRNA targets [91, 92]. When multiple transcripts compete for a shared, limiting pool of miRNAs, repression becomes a collective process rather than an independent, target-specific one. As a consequence, stochastic fluctuations in the expression of one target propagate to others through competition for miRNA binding [93–95], Figure 3e,f. Near the threshold, where all coupled ultrasensitive modules operate in their most responsive regime, this leads to strongly correlated—and effectively synchronized—fluctuations among targets, reflecting the collective amplification and transmission of stochastic perturbations [22]. These predictions have been supported by transcriptome-wide analyses revealing correlated expression patterns among miRNA targets [96] and by single-cell experiments [45, 97].

Importantly, the presence of a nonlinear threshold in this near-equimolar regime also creates the conditions under which bimodal expression distributions can emerge at the population level, Figure 3c,f. Crucially, such bimodality does not require deterministic bistability. Instead, it can arise from the interplay between nonlinear regulatory thresholds and extrinsic noise in other-

wise monostable systems [98]. Extrinsic variability allows cells to sample different regions of a nonlinear input–output curve, while the threshold converts continuous fluctuations into discrete population-level expression states [99–101]. This mechanism provides a natural explanation for the appearance of bimodal or multimodal distributions near the titration threshold. At the phenotypic level, this discrete heterogeneity can be functional: bimodality biases cells toward discrete expression modes rather than a continuous spectrum - supporting cell fate decisions [102, 103], Figure 3g. Explicit modeling of miRNA binding dynamics further indicates that multiple binding sites can give rise to sustained oscillations even in the absence of canonical feedback loops [23]. While such oscillatory dynamics offer an additional dynamical route to population-level variability, how they are converted into stable phenotypic states remains an open question, likely requiring coupling to slower regulatory processes or to network-level interactions.

Beyond their established role in controlling gene expression noise, miRNAs can also influence the temporal dynamics of gene regulation. Timing is essential for many cellular processes, as they rely on precise temporal organization, such as during cell cycle, cell-fate decisions and differentiation [104]. Many of these downstream processes are triggered when a regulator reaches a threshold concentration. However, since gene expression is inherently stochastic, there is a degree of uncertainty in threshold crossing time with potential consequences for biological functions. Several works have explored how these fluctuations can be controlled, where regulatory motifs have had a central role [104–106]. In particular, post-transcriptional regulation by small RNAs has been shown to theoretically modulate the distribution and efficiency of threshold crossing times, providing a mechanism to reduce timing variability and tune first-passage dynamics. Post-transcriptional regulation can attain a higher timing precision than transcrip-

tional regulation for comparable protein levels [107–109]. These results suggest that miRNA-mediated regulation provides a flexible mechanism to control both the precision and reliability of timing in stochastic gene expression [108].

Noise regulation by miRNAs is further constrained by bioenergetic costs. Efe Ilker et al. [110] showed that post-transcriptional noise reduction entails metabolic costs associated with increased RNA turnover and reduced translational efficiency, suggesting an evolutionary trade-off between robustness and energetic efficiency.

Finally, a network-level perspective is essential. Gene expression plasticity correlates more strongly with overall regulatory network complexity than with specific canonical motifs [111]. In this view, miRNAs act as pervasive regulators that modulate burst amplitude, thresholds, correlations, temporal filtering, and energetic cost across many targets, collectively shaping robustness and plasticity at the network scale.

Discussion

MiRNA-mediated regulation has traditionally been interpreted through a steady-state lens, emphasizing repression strength and mean expression control. However, as discussed throughout this review, a unifying theme emerges when these interactions are examined dynamically: the same molecular sequestration mechanism that generates threshold-like behavior also endows post-transcriptional circuits with rich temporal and stochastic processing capabilities.

Indeed, ultrasensitivity does not merely define a static repression boundary, but determines how signal timing and fluctuations are processed. On one side, sequestration introduces intrinsic timescales through binding, unbinding, and degradation kinetics, enabling post-transcriptional circuits to respond selectively to temporal patterns of upstream activity. Modeling studies indicate that such systems can ex-

hibit frequency preference and transient band-pass behavior, implying that miRNAs are potential decoders of temporal information. On the other side, the same nonlinear threshold reshapes how fluctuations are transmitted. Far from the threshold, miRNAs buffer variability by limiting burst amplitude and dampening transcriptional noise. In contrast, near equimolarity, nonlinear amplification converts small stochastic differences into discrete population-level outcomes, enabling bimodality without deterministic bistability. In this way, ultrasensitivity acts as a conditional modulator of variability, either a stabilizer of gene expression or a generator of heterogeneity depending on stoichiometry.

An important open question concerns how temporal decoding operates under intrinsic stochastic fluctuations in gene expression. Gene expression is inherently noisy, which fundamentally constrains how accurately dynamic signals can be interpreted. Several studies have addressed the interplay between temporal decoding and stochastic fluctuations at transcriptional level. At transcriptional level, there is a fundamental trade-off between decoding input dynamics and minimizing gene expression noise. Although the cell can exploit different promoter classes to differentially control gene expression using transcription factor dynamics, gene expression noise fundamentally limits how much information can be encoded in the dynamics of a single transcription factor and reliably decoded by promoters [68, 112].

Despite these constraints, temporal modulation of inputs can reshape how noise impacts gene regulation. Oscillatory signals have been analytically shown to reduce output variability for some biologically relevant parameter regime, producing more stable protein levels than constant inputs [113]. More generally, oscillatory perturbations have been proposed as powerful probes of stochastic genetic networks, capable of revealing dynamical properties and characteristic timescales that remain hidden under

static stimulation [114]. From an information-theoretic perspective, dynamic inputs can also enhance signal transmission: oscillatory signals can exhibit a resonant frequency that maximizes information transfer, with the optimal response determined by underlying biophysical constraints [115].

Moreover, noise itself can play an active functional role in dynamic decoding. Biochemical noise can enhance entrainment and amplifications of NF- κ B oscillations under periodic TNF stimulation, leading to an increase in transcriptional efficiency [116]. More broadly, noise can interact constructively with time-varying inputs in nonlinear regulatory systems, exhibiting phenomena such as stochastic resonance and noise-enhanced signal discrimination [117, 118].

Extending these concepts beyond transcriptional regulation raises the possibility that similar mechanisms could operate at post-transcriptional level. In particular, the interplay between temporal modulation and stochasticity may influence miRNA-mediated regulation, shaping both target selectivity and robustness. The observation of resonance-like behavior in RNA interference dynamics [119] suggests that analogous effects may also operate at miRNA-based regulatory systems.

Post-transcriptional regulation by miRNAs provides a powerful mechanism to control the temporal dynamics of gene expression programs. In several developmental contexts, miRNA-mediated interactions have been shown to shape the progression and timing of cell-fate transitions by modulating regulatory thresholds and dynamical regimes, including bistability and oscillations [23, 120, 121]. At the same time, theoretical and experimental work incorporating stochasticity has demonstrated that miRNA-dependent circuits can influence the heterogeneity of differentiation timing across cell populations, linking gene expression noise to variability in fate decisions [122].

Moreover, post-transcriptional regulation can directly impact the precision of timing by mod-

ulating threshold-crossing dynamics in stochastic gene expression, in some cases achieving higher temporal accuracy than transcriptional control at comparable expression levels [107–109]. Together, these results suggest that miRNA-mediated regulation may not only govern the timing of cellular transitions but can also tune their reliability across fluctuating environments. In this context, a relevant open question is whether oscillatory control of miRNA expression can influence not only mean expression levels, but also the precision of timing, for instance by reshaping the distribution of threshold-crossing times, thereby extending previous results on oscillatory regulation [123].

The broader picture is that miRNAs contribute to gene regulatory computation. Through their characteristic titration-based behavior, they implement nonlinear transformations, they introduce characteristic timescales, they couple multiple targets and they control noise amplitude. These features resemble computational primitives used in synthetic and neuromorphic systems, suggesting that miRNAs may function as distributed information-processing layers embedded within transcriptional circuits. In particular, sequestration-based motifs can implement threshold-like behaviors and frequency selective filters, supporting the idea that miRNAs may serve as biomolecular building blocks for recurrent neural-like computation. In this view, gene regulatory circuits could perform operations analogous to those found in artificial neural networks [124, 125].

Viewing miRNA-mediated regulation through a dynamical lens portrays their role as active information processing units rather than merely passive repressors. The underlying titration mechanism that defines repression strength at steady state can also give rise to temporal filtering, noise modulation, and nonlinear decision-making in time-dependent contexts. Static measurements of expression are insufficient to capture the functional repertoire of miRNAs; instead, time-resolved, single-cell, and perturba-

tive approaches will be essential to disentangle how kinetic parameters, molecular abundances, and fluctuating inputs jointly determine regulatory outcomes. This perspective reflects an expanded view of gene regulation in which time emerges as a defining dimension, and regulatory control arises from the interplay of multiple layers acting in concert to shape dynamic and stochastic cellular behaviors.

References

- [1] David P. Bartel. Metazoan MicroRNAs. *Cell*, 173(1):20–51, 2018.
- [2] Stanley D. Chandradoss, Nicole T. Schirle, Malwina Szczepaniak, Ian J. MacRae, and Chirlmin Joo. A Dynamic Search Process Underlies MicroRNA Targeting. *Cell*, 162(1):96–107, 7 2015.
- [3] Sonia Guil and Manel Esteller. RNA–RNA interactions in gene regulation: the coding and noncoding players. *Trends in Biochemical Sciences*, 40(5):248–256, 5 2015.
- [4] Thomas B. Hansen, Trine I. Jensen, Bettina H. Clausen, Jesper B. Bramsen, Bente Finsen, Christian K. Damgaard, and Jørgen Kjems. Natural RNA circles function as efficient microRNA sponges. *Nature*, 495(7441):384–388, 3 2013.
- [5] Sergej Djuranovic, Ali Nahvi, and Rachel Green. miRNA-Mediated Gene Silencing by Translational Repression Followed by mRNA Deadenylation and Decay. *Science*, 336(6078):237–240, 4 2012.
- [6] Xin Lai, Ulf Schmitz, Shailendra K. Gupta, Animesh Bhattacharya, Manfred Kunz, Olaf Wolkenhauer, and Julio Vera. Computational analysis of target hub gene repression regulated by multiple and

Acknowledgments

CB acknowledges support from the European REA and Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions, grant agreement no. 101131463 (SIMBAD).

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s)

cooperative miRNAs. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 40(18):8818–8834, 10 2012.

- [7] Allan M. Gurtan and Phillip A. Sharp. The Role of miRNAs in Regulating Gene Expression Networks. *Journal of Molecular Biology*, 425(19):3582–3600, 10 2013.
- [8] Eugene Berezikov. Evolution of microRNA diversity and regulation in animals. *Nature Reviews Genetics*, 12(12):846–860, 12 2011.
- [9] Anagha Joshi, Yvonne Beck, and Tom Michoel. Post-transcriptional regulatory networks play a key role in noise reduction that is conserved from microorganisms to mammals. *The FEBS Journal*, 279(18):3501–3512, 9 2012.
- [10] Mattia Miotto, Enzo Marinari, and Andrea De Martino. Competing endogenous RNA crosstalk at system level. *PLOS Computational Biology*, 15(11):e1007474, 11 2019.
- [11] Shankar Mukherji, Margaret S. Ebert, Grace X.Y. Zheng, John S. Tsang, Phillip A. Sharp, and Alexander Van Oudenaarden. MicroRNAs can generate thresholds in target gene expression. *Nature Genetics*, 43(9):854–859, 2011.
- [12] Marcelo Behar and Alexander Hoffmann. Understanding the temporal codes of

- intra-cellular signals. *Current Opinion in Genetics and Development*, 20(6):684–693, 12 2010.
- [13] Jeremy E. Purvis and Galit Lahav. Encoding and decoding cellular information through signaling dynamics, 2 2013.
- [14] Miki Ebisuya and James Briscoe. What does time mean in development? *Development*, 145(12), 6 2018.
- [15] Takao Ishidate, Ahmed Elewa, Soyoung Kim, Craig C Mello, and Masaki Shirayama. Divide and differentiate. *Cell Cycle*, 13(9):1384–1391, 5 2014.
- [16] Nitin Kapadia and Paul Nurse. Spatiotemporal orchestration of mitosis by cyclin-dependent kinase. *Nature*, 643(8074):1391–1399, 7 2025.
- [17] Diya Banerjee and Frank Slack. Control of developmental timing by small temporal RNAs: a paradigm for RNA-mediated regulation of gene expression. *BioEssays*, 24(2):119–129, 2 2002.
- [18] G.D. Hayes and G. Ruvkun. Misexpression of the *Caenorhabditis elegans* miRNA let-7 Is Sufficient to Drive Developmental Programs. *Cold Spring Harbor Symposia on Quantitative Biology*, 71(0):21–27, 1 2006.
- [19] Kathryn N. Ivey and Deepak Srivastava. MicroRNAs as Regulators of Differentiation and Cell Fate Decisions. *Cell Stem Cell*, 7(1):36–41, 7 2010.
- [20] Eric G. Moss. Heterochronic Genes and the Nature of Developmental Time. *Current Biology*, 17(11):R425–R434, 6 2007.
- [21] Nicolas E. Buchler and Matthieu Louis. Molecular Titration and Ultrasensitivity in Regulatory Networks. *Journal of Molecular Biology*, 384(5):1106–1119, 2008.
- [22] Carla Bosia, Andrea Pagnani, and Riccardo Zecchina. Modelling Competing Endogenous RNA Networks. *PLoS ONE*, 8(6), 2013.
- [23] Benjamin Nordick, Polly Y. Yu, Guangyuan Liao, and Tian Hong. Nonmodular oscillator and switch based on RNA decay drive regeneration of multimodal gene expression. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 50(7):3693–3708, 2022.
- [24] Qiang Zhang, Sudin Bhattacharya, and Melvin E. Andersen. Ultrasensitive response motifs: Basic amplifiers in molecular signalling networks. *Open Biology*, 3:130031, 4 2013.
- [25] Michael A. Savageau and Robert. Rosen. *Biochemical systems analysis : a study of function and design in molecular biology*. Addison-Wesley Pub. Co., Advanced Book Program, 1976.
- [26] A. Goldbeter and D. E. Koshland. Sensitivity amplification in biochemical systems. *Quarterly Reviews of Biophysics*, 15(3):555–591, 8 1982.
- [27] James E. Ferrell and Sang Hoon Ha. Ultrasensitivity part I: Michaelian responses and zero-order ultrasensitivity. *Trends in Biochemical Sciences*, 39(10):496–503, 10 2014.
- [28] Jeremy Gunawardena. Multisite protein phosphorylation makes a good threshold but can be a poor switch. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 102(41):14617–14622, 10 2005.
- [29] Nicolas E Buchler and Frederick R Cross. Protein sequestration generates a flexible

- ultrasensitive response in a genetic network. *Molecular Systems Biology*, 5(1), 1 2009.
- [30] Xiao Jun Tian, Hang Zhang, Jingyu Zhang, and Jianhua Xing. Reciprocal regulation between mRNA and microRNA enables a bistable switch that directs cell fate decisions. *FEBS Letters*, 590:3443–3455, 2016.
- [31] Stephen M. Cohen, Julius Brennecke, and Alexander Stark. Denoising feedback loops by thresholding—a new role for microRNAs: Figure 1. *Genes & Development*, 20(20):2769–2772, 10 2006.
- [32] Eitan Rotem, Adiel Loinger, Irine Ronin, Irit Levin-Reisman, Chana Gabay, Noam Shores, Ofer Biham, and Nathalie Q. Balaban. Regulation of phenotypic variability by a threshold-based mechanism underlies bacterial persistence. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 107(28):12541–12546, 7 2010.
- [33] Daniel Jost, Andrzej Nowojewski, and Erel Levine. Small RNA biology is systems biology. *BMB Reports*, 44(1):11–21, 1 2011.
- [34] Erel Levine, Zhongge Zhang, Thomas Kuhlman, and Terence Hwa. Quantitative characteristics of gene regulation by small RNA. *PLoS Biology*, 5(9):1998–2010, 2007.
- [35] Yan Li, Fay Wang, Jin-A Lee, and Fen-Biao Gao. MicroRNA-9a ensures the precise specification of sensory organ precursors in *Drosophila*. *Genes & Development*, 20(20):2793–2805, 10 2006.
- [36] György Hutvagner and Phillip D. Zamore. A microRNA in a Multiple-Turnover RNAi Enzyme Complex. *Science*, 297(5589):2056–2060, 9 2002.
- [37] Alessia Baccharini, Hemangini Chauhan, Thomas J. Gardner, Anitha D. Jayaprakash, Ravi Sachidanandam, and Brian D. Brown. Kinetic Analysis Reveals the Fate of a MicroRNA following Target Regulation in Mammalian Cells. *Current Biology*, 21(5):369–376, 3 2011.
- [38] Saibal Chatterjee and Helge Großhans. Active turnover modulates mature microRNA activity in *Caenorhabditis elegans*. *Nature*, 461(7263):546–549, 9 2009.
- [39] Sophie Bail, Mavis Swerdel, Hudan Liu, Xinfu Jiao, Loyal A. Goff, Ronald P. Hart, and Megerditch Kiledjian. Differential regulation of microRNA stability. *RNA*, 16(5):1032–1039, 5 2010.
- [40] Swadesh K. Das, Upneet K. Sokhi, Sujit K. Bhutia, Belal Azab, Zhao-zhong Su, Devanand Sarkar, and Paul B. Fisher. Human polynucleotide phosphorylase selectively and preferentially degrades microRNA-221 in human melanoma cells. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 107(26):11948–11953, 6 2010.
- [41] Manuel de la Mata, Dimos Gaidatzis, Mirela Vitanescu, Michael B Stadler, Corinna Wentzel, Peter Scheiffele, Witold Filipowicz, and Helge Großhans. Potent degradation of neuronal miRNAs induced by highly complementary targets. *EMBO reports*, 16(4):500–511, 4 2015.
- [42] Jean Hausser, Afzal Pasha Syed, Nathalie Selevsek, Erik van Nimwegen, Lukasz Jaskiewicz, Ruedi Aebersold, and Mihaela Zavolan. Timescales and bottlenecks in miRNA-dependent gene regulation. *Molecular Systems Biology*, 9(1), 1 2013.

- [43] Boyan Bonev, Peter Stanley, and Nancy Papalopulu. MicroRNA-9 Modulates Hes1 Ultradian Oscillations by Forming a Double-Negative Feedback Loop. *Cell Reports*, 2(1):10–18, 7 2012.
- [44] Mati Mann, Arnav Mehta, Jimmy L. Zhao, Kevin Lee, Georgi K. Marinov, Yvette Garcia-Flores, Li-Fan Lu, Alexander Y. Rudensky, and David Baltimore. An NF- κ B-microRNA regulatory network tunes macrophage inflammatory responses. *Nature Communications*, 8(1):851, 10 2017.
- [45] Carla Bosia, Francesco Sgrò, Laura Conti, Carlo Baldassi, Davide Brusa, Federica Cavallo, Ferdinando Di Cunto, Emilia Turco, Andrea Pagnani, and Riccardo Zecchina. RNAs competing for microRNAs mutually influence their fluctuations in a highly non-linear microRNA-dependent manner in single cells. *Genome Biology*, 18(1):37, 12 2017.
- [46] Rosa Martinez-Corral and Jordi Garcia-Ojalvo. Modeling cellular regulation by pulsatile inputs. *Current Opinion in Systems Biology*, 3:23–29, 6 2017.
- [47] Joe Levine, Yihan Lin, and Michael Elowitz. Functional Roles of Pulsing in Genetic Circuits. *Science*, 342(6163):1188–1193, 2013.
- [48] Akihiro Isomura and Ryoichiro Kageyama. Ultradian oscillations and pulses: coordinating cellular responses and cell fate decisions. *Development*, 141(19):3627–3636, 10 2014.
- [49] John G. Albeck, Gordon B. Mills, and Joan S. Brugge. Frequency-Modulated Pulses of ERK Activity Transmit Quantitative Proliferation Signals. *Molecular Cell*, 49(2):249–261, 1 2013.
- [50] Keng Boon Wee, Wee Kheng Yio, Uttam Surana, and Keng Hwee Chiam. Transcription factor oscillations induce differential gene expressions. *Biophysical Journal*, 102(11):2413–2423, 6 2012.
- [51] Zongmao Gao, Siheng Chen, Shanshan Qin, and Chao Tang. Network Motifs Capable of Decoding Transcription Factor Dynamics. *Scientific Reports*, 8(1):1–10, 2018.
- [52] Carolyn Zhang, Ryan Tsoi, Feilun Wu, and Lingchong You. Processing Oscillatory Signals by Incoherent Feedforward Loops. *PLoS Computational Biology*, 12(9):1–16, 2016.
- [53] Dirk Benzinger, Serguei Ovinnikov, and Mustafa Khammash. Synthetic gene networks recapitulate dynamic signal decoding and differential gene expression. *Cell Systems*, 13(5):353–364, 5 2022.
- [54] Marko Marhl, Matjaž Perc, and Stefan Schuster. Selective regulation of cellular processes via protein cascades acting as band-pass filters for time-limited oscillations. *FEBS Letters*, 579(25):5461–5465, 10 2005.
- [55] Luca Cerone and Zoltán Neufeld. Differential gene expression regulated by oscillatory transcription factors. *PLoS ONE*, 7(1), 2012.
- [56] Axel Cournac and Jacques Alexandre Sepulchre. Simple molecular networks that respond optimally to time-periodic stimulation. *BMC Systems Biology*, 3, 3 2009.
- [57] Juliana Reves Szemere, Horacio G. Rotstein, and Alejandra C. Ventura. Frequency-preference response in covalent modification cycles under substrate sequestration conditions. *npj Systems Biology and Applications*, 7(1), 12 2021.

- [58] Yichi Zhang, Christian Cuba Samaniego, Katelyn Carleton, Yili Qian, Giulia Giordano, and Elisa Franco. Building molecular band-pass filters via molecular sequestration. In *2022 IEEE 61st Conference on Decision and Control (CDC)*, pages 3890–3895. bioRxiv, IEEE, 4 2022.
- [59] Mariama El Baroudi, Davide Corà, Carla Bosia, Matteo Osella, and Michele Caselle. A Curated Database of miRNA Mediated Feed-Forward Loops Involving MYC as Master Regulator. *PLoS ONE*, 6(3):e14742, 3 2011.
- [60] Dong hyun Kim, Dominic Grün, and Alexander van Oudenaarden. Dampening of expression oscillations by synchronous regulation of a microRNA and its target. *Nature Genetics*, 45(11):1337–1344, 11 2013.
- [61] Davide Cora’, Angela Re, Michele Caselle, and Federico Bussolino. MicroRNA-mediated regulatory circuits: outlook and perspectives. *Physical Biology*, 14(4):045001, 6 2017.
- [62] Elsi Ferro, Chiara Enrico Bena, Silvia Grigolon, and Carla Bosia. From Endogenous to Synthetic microRNA-Mediated Regulatory Circuits: An Overview. *Cells*, 8(12):1540, 11 2019.
- [63] Simone Tealdi, Elsi Ferro, Carlo Cosimo Campa, and Carla Bosia. microRNA-Mediated Encoding and Decoding of Time-Dependent Signals in Tumorigenesis. *Biomolecules*, 12(2):1–19, 2022.
- [64] Candela L. Szischik, Juliana Reves Szemere, Rocío Balderrama, Constanza Sánchez de la Vega, and Alejandra C. Ventura. Transient frequency preference responses in cell signaling systems. *npj Systems Biology and Applications*, 10(1), 12 2024.
- [65] Matteo Figliuzzi, Andrea De Martino, and Enzo Marinari. RNA-based regulation: Dynamics and response to perturbations of competing RNAs. *Biophysical Journal*, 107(4):1011–1022, 2014.
- [66] Elsi Ferro, Candela Szischik, Alejandra C. Ventura, and Carla Bosia. The advantage of periodic over constant signalling in microRNA-mediated regulation. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 53(17), 9 2025.
- [67] Nan Hao and Erin K. O’Shea. Signal-dependent dynamics of transcription factor translocation controls gene expression. *Nature Structural and Molecular Biology*, 19(1):31–40, 1 2012.
- [68] Anders S. Hansen and Erin K. O’Shea. Encoding four gene expression programs in the activation dynamics of a single transcription factor. *Current Biology*, 26(7):R269–R271, 2016.
- [69] Shunbin Xu, P Dane Witmer, Stephen Lumayag, Beatrix Kovacs, and David Valle. MicroRNA (miRNA) transcriptome of mouse retina and identification of a sensory organ-specific miRNA cluster. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 282(34):25053–25066, 2007.
- [70] Hai Ying M. Cheng, Joseph W. Papp, Olga Varlamova, Heather Dziema, Brandon Russell, John P. Curfman, Takanobu Nakazawa, Kimiko Shimizu, Hitoshi Okamura, Soren Impey, and Karl Obrietan. microRNA Modulation of Circadian-Clock Period and Entrainment. *Neuron*, 54(5):813–829, 6 2007.
- [71] Maocheng Yang, Jung Eun Lee, Richard W. Padgett, and Isaac Edery. Circadian regulation of a limited set

- of conserved microRNAs in *Drosophila*. *BMC Genomics*, 9, 2 2008.
- [72] Jingkui Wang, Laura Symul, Jake Yeung, Cédric Gobet, Jonathan Sobel, Sarah Lück, Pål O. Westermark, Nacho Molina, and Felix Naef. Circadian clock-dependent and -independent posttranscriptional regulation underlies temporal mRNA accumulation in mouse liver. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 115(8), 2 2018.
- [73] Caroline C. Friedel, Lars Dölken, Zsolt Ruzsics, Ulrich H. Koszinowski, and Ralf Zimmer. Conserved principles of mammalian transcriptional regulation revealed by RNA half-life. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 37(17):e115–e115, 9 2009.
- [74] Michael B. Elowitz, Arnold J. Levine, Eric D. Siggia, and Peter S. Swain. Stochastic Gene Expression in a Single Cell. *Science*, 297(5584):1183–1186, 8 2002.
- [75] Peter S. Swain, Michael B. Elowitz, and Eric D. Siggia. Intrinsic and extrinsic contributions to stochasticity in gene expression. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 99(20):12795–12800, 10 2002.
- [76] Arjun Raj and Alexander van Oudenaarden. Nature, Nurture, or Chance: Stochastic Gene Expression and Its Consequences. *Cell*, 135(2):216–226, 10 2008.
- [77] Mukund Thattai and Alexander van Oudenaarden. Intrinsic noise in gene regulatory networks. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 98(15):8614–8619, 7 2001.
- [78] Nir Friedman, Long Cai, and X. Sunney Xie. Linking Stochastic Dynamics to Population Distribution: An Analytical Framework of Gene Expression. *Physical Review Letters*, 97(16):168302, 10 2006.
- [79] Marco Antonio Valencia-Sanchez, Jidong Liu, Gregory J. Hannon, and Roy Parker. Control of translation and mRNA degradation by miRNAs and siRNAs. *Genes & Development*, 20(5):515–524, 3 2006.
- [80] Jörn M. Schmiedel, Sandy L. Klemm, Yannan Zheng, Apratim Sahay, Nils Blüthgen, Debora S. Marks, and Alexander van Oudenaarden. MicroRNA control of protein expression noise. *Science*, 348(6230):128–132, 4 2015.
- [81] Luca Laurenti, Attila Csikasz-Nagy, Marta Kwiatkowska, and Luca Cardelli. Molecular Filters for Noise Reduction. *Biophysical Journal*, 114(12):3000–3011, 6 2018.
- [82] Matteo Osella, Carla Bosia, Davide Corá, and Michele Caselle. The role of incoherent microRNA-mediated feedforward loops in noise buffering. *PLoS computational biology*, 7(3):e1001101, 2011.
- [83] Matteo Osella, Andrea Riba, Alessandro Testori, Davide Corà, and Michele Caselle. Interplay of microRNA and epigenetic regulation in the human regulatory network. *Frontiers in genetics*, 5:345, 2014.
- [84] Velia Siciliano, Immacolata Garzilli, Chiara Fracassi, Stefania Criscuolo, Simona Ventre, and Diego Di Bernardo. MiRNAs confer phenotypic robustness to gene networks by suppressing biological noise. *Nature Communications*, 4, 2013.
- [85] Silvia Grigolon, Francesca Di Patti, Andrea De Martino, and Enzo Marinari. Noise processing by microRNA-mediated circuits: the incoherent feed-

- forward loop, revisited. *Heliyon*, 2(4), 2016.
- [86] Carla Bosia, Matteo Osella, Mariama El Baroudi, Davide Corà, and Michele Caselle. Gene autoregulation via intronic microRNAs and its functions. *BMC systems biology*, 6:1–16, 2012.
- [87] Andrea Riba, Carla Bosia, Mariama El Baroudi, Laura Ollino, and Michele Caselle. A Combination of Transcriptional and MicroRNA Regulation Improves the Stability of the Relative Concentrations of Target Genes. *PLoS Computational Biology*, 10(2):e1003490, 2 2014.
- [88] Timothy J. Strovas, Alexander B. Rosenberg, Brianna E. Kuypers, Richard A. Muscat, and Georg Seelig. MicroRNA-Based Single-Gene Circuits Buffer Protein Synthesis Rates against Perturbations. *ACS Synthetic Biology*, 3(5):324–331, 5 2014.
- [89] Matteo Figliuzzi, Enzo Marinari, and Andrea De Martino. MicroRNAs as a selective channel of communication between competing RNAs: A steady-state theory. *Biophysical Journal*, 104(5):1203–1213, 2013.
- [90] Domitilla Del Vecchio, Alexander J Ninfa, and Eduardo D Sontag. Modular cell biology: retroactivity and insulation. *Molecular Systems Biology*, 4(1), 1 2008.
- [91] Leonardo Salmena, Laura Poliseno, Yvonne Tay, Lev Kats, and Pier Paolo Pandolfi. A ceRNA hypothesis: The rosetta stone of a hidden RNA language? *Cell*, 146(3):353–358, 2011.
- [92] Ugo Ala, Florian A. Karreth, Carla Bosia, Andrea Pagnani, Riccardo Taulli, Valentine Leópol, Yvonne Tay, Paolo Provero, Riccardo Zecchina, and Pier Paolo Pandolfi. Integrated transcriptional and competitive endogenous RNA networks are cross-regulated in permissive molecular environments. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 110(18):7154–7159, 2013.
- [93] Xin Lai, Olaf Wolkenhauer, and Julio Vera. Understanding microRNA-mediated gene regulatory networks through mathematical modelling. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 44(13):6019–6035, 2016.
- [94] Araks Martirosyan, Marco Del Giudice, Chiara Enrico Bena, Andrea Pagnani, Carla Bosia, and Andrea De Martino. Kinetic modelling of competition and depletion of shared miRNAs by competing endogenous RNAs. In Xin Lai, Shailendra K. Gupta, and Julio Vera, editors, *Methods in Molecular Biology*, volume 1912, pages 367–409. Springer New York, New York, NY, 2019.
- [95] Elsi Ferro, Candela L Szischik, Marta Cunial, Ventura Alejandra C, Andrea De Martino, and Carla Bosia. Out-of-Equilibrium ceRNA Crosstalk. In Xin Lai, Shailendra Gupta, and Julio Vera Gonzalez, editors, *Computational Biology of Non-Coding RNA: Methods and Protocols*, pages 167–193. Springer US, New York, NY, 2025.
- [96] Andrzej J Rzepiela, Souvik Ghosh, Jeremie Breda, Arnau Vina-Vilaseca, Afzal P Syed, Andreas J Gruber, Katja Eschbach, Christian Beisel, Erik van Nimwegen, and Mihaela Zavolan. Single-cell mRNA profiling reveals the hierarchical response of miRNA targets to miRNA induction. *Molecular Systems Biology*, 14(8), 8 2018.

- [97] Ye Yuan, Bing Liu, Peng Xie, Michael Q. Zhang, Yanda Li, Zhen Xie, and Xiaowo Wang. Model-guided quantitative analysis of microRNA-mediated regulation on competing endogenous RNAs using a synthetic gene circuit. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 112(10):3158–3163, 2015.
- [98] Lev S. Tsimring. Noise in biology. *Reports on Progress in Physics*, 77(2), 2 2014.
- [99] Marco Del Giudice, Stefano Bo, Silvia Grigolon, and Carla Bosia. On the role of extrinsic noise in microRNA-mediated bimodal gene expression. *PLoS computational biology*, 14(4):e1006063, 2018.
- [100] Marco Del Giudice, Carla Bosia, Silvia Grigolon, and Stefano Bo. Stochastic sequestration dynamics: A minimal model with extrinsic noise for bimodal distributions and competitors correlation. *Scientific Reports*, 8(1), 12 2018.
- [101] Raunak Adhikary, Arnab Roy, Mohit Kumar Jolly, and Dipjyoti Das. Effects of microRNA-mediated negative feedback on gene expression noise. *Biophysical Journal*, 122(21):4220–4240, 11 2023.
- [102] Salil Garg and Phillip A. Sharp. Single-cell variability guided by microRNAs. *Science*, 352(6292):1390–1391, 6 2016.
- [103] Meenakshi Chakraborty, Sofia Hu, Erica Visness, Marco Del Giudice, Andrea De Martino, Carla Bosia, Phillip A Sharp, and Salil Garg. MicroRNAs organize intrinsic variation into stem cell states. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 12(117), 3 2020.
- [104] Juan M Pedraza and Johan Paulsson. Random timing in signaling cascades. *Molecular Systems Biology*, 3(1), 1 2007.
- [105] Alma Dal Co, Marco Cosentino Lagomarsino, Michele Caselle, and Matteo Osella. Stochastic timing in gene expression for simple regulatory strategies. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 45(3):1069–1078, 2 2017.
- [106] Amnon Amir, Oren Kobiler, Assaf Rokney, Amos B Oppenheim, and Joel Stavans. Noise in timing and precision of gene activities in a genetic cascade. *Molecular Systems Biology*, 3(1), 1 2007.
- [107] Kuheli Biswas and Anandamohan Ghosh. Timing efficiency in small-RNA-regulated post-transcriptional processes. *Physical Review E*, 101(2), 2 2020.
- [108] Kuheli Biswas, Mohit Kumar Jolly, and Anandamohan Ghosh. First passage time properties of miRNA-mediated protein translation. *Journal of Theoretical Biology*, 529, 2021.
- [109] Syed Yunus Ali, Ashok Prasad, and Dibyendu Das. Exact distributions of threshold crossing times of proteins under post-transcriptional regulation by small RNAs. *Physical Review E*, 111(1):014405, 1 2025.
- [110] Efe Ilker and Michael Hinczewski. Bioenergetic costs and the evolution of noise regulation by microRNAs. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 121:e2308796121, 2024.
- [111] Apolline J R Petit, Anne Genissel, and Arnaud Le Rouzic. Gene expression plasticity is associated with regulatory complexity but not with specific network motifs. *GENETICS*, 232(4), 4 2026.

- [112] Anders S. Hansen and Erin K. O’Shea. Promoter decoding of transcription factor dynamics involves a trade-off between noise and control of gene expression. *Molecular Systems Biology*, 9(704), 2013.
- [113] Filipe Tostevin, Wiet De Ronde, and Pieter Rein Ten Wolde. Reliability of frequency and amplitude decoding in gene regulation. *Physical Review Letters*, 108(10), 3 2012.
- [114] Ovidiu Lipan and Wing H. Wong. The use of oscillatory signals in the study of genetic networks. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 102(20):7063–7068, 5 2005.
- [115] Andrew Mugler, Aleksandra M. Walczak, and Chris H. Wiggins. Information-optimal transcriptional response to oscillatory driving. *Physical Review Letters*, 105(5), 7 2010.
- [116] Ryan A. Kellogg and Savaş Tay. Noise facilitates transcriptional control under dynamic inputs. *Cell*, 160(3):381–392, 1 2015.
- [117] Yong Xu, Juan Wu, Lin Du, and Hui Yang. Stochastic resonance in a genetic toggle model with harmonic excitation and Lévy noise. *Chaos, Solitons & Fractals*, 92:91–100, 2016.
- [118] Canjun Wang, Ming Yi, Keli Yang, and Lijian Yang. Time delay induced transition of gene switch and stochastic resonance in a genetic transcriptional regulatory model. *BMC systems biology*, 6:1–16, 2012.
- [119] Shyamtanu Chattoraj, Shekhar Saha, Sidhartha Sankar Jana, and Kankan Bhattacharyya. Dynamics of gene silencing in a live cell: stochastic resonance. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry Letters*, 5(6):1012–1016, 2014.
- [120] Marc Goodfellow, Nicholas E Phillips, Cerys Manning, Tobias Galla, and Nancy Papalopulu. MicroRNA input into a neural ultradian oscillator controls emergence and timing of alternative cell states. *Nature communications*, 5(1):3399, 2014.
- [121] Ximena Soto, Veronica Biga, Jochen Kursawe, Robert Lea, Parnian Doostdar, Riba Thomas, and Nancy Papalopulu. Dynamic properties of noise and Her6 levels are optimized by miR-9, allowing the decoding of the Her6 oscillator. *The EMBO Journal*, 39(12), 6 2020.
- [122] Nick E Phillips, Cerys S Manning, Tom Pettini, Veronica Biga, Elli Marinopoulou, Peter Stanley, James Boyd, James Bagnall, Pawel Paszek, David G Spiller, Michael RH White, Marc Goodfellow, Tobias Galla, Magnus Rattray, and Nancy Papalopulu. Stochasticity in the miR-9/Hes1 oscillatory network can account for clonal heterogeneity in the timing of differentiation. *eLife*, 5, 10 2016.
- [123] Kuheli Biswas, Mayank Shreshtha, Anudeep Surendran, and Anandamohan Ghosh. First-passage time statistics of stochastic transcription process for time-dependent reaction rates. *European Physical Journal E*, 42(2), 2 2019.
- [124] Andrew Moorman, Christian Cuba Samaniego, Carlo Maley, and Ron Weiss. A Dynamical Biomolecular Neural Network. In *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Decision and Control*, volume 2019-December, pages 1797–1802. Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Inc., 12 2019.

[125] Frank Britto Bisso, Durga Shree, Yinan Zhu, and Christian Cuba Samaniego. De-

sign principles of neuromorphic computing using genetic circuits. 12 2025.

Fig 1

Fig 2

Fig 3

Figure Captions

Figure 1. Ultrasensitivity in miRNA-mRNA threshold-linear curves. **a.** miRNA-mRNA interaction models. Top: canonical miRNA-mRNA binding interaction. Bottom left: classic molecular titration model as per [21]. Bottom right: miRNA-mRNA interaction model. The rates of synthesis of M and R are represented by k_M and k_R , respectively, the rates of basal degradation for each species are g_M and g_R . The binding is represented by the constant κ , which determines the rate of complex formation. The complex degradation rate is given by the constant γ . Two recycling rates are considered: α represents the miRNA recycling rate, which is expected to be lower than 1 since the miRNA-mRNA interaction is considered to be multiple turnover; β is the mRNA recycling rate, and while it is typically equal to 1, it can also contemplate scenarios where a single mRNA can trigger multiple miRNA molecules' degradation. **b.** Free species abundance plots for a sub-catalytic model with $\alpha \neq 0$. Top: Linear plot. Center: Logarithmic plot with the logarithmic gain ($G = \frac{d \log(R)}{d \log(k_R)}$) shown with a black dotted line. Inset: Logarithmic gain calculated for each point in the R abundance plot. A maximum is reached near the threshold value. Bottom: Free R abundance plot in log scale for different times. A threshold appears at every measured time. **c.** Logarithmic plots of free species abundance for a perfectly catalytic model ($\alpha = 0$). Top: Steady state plot, no threshold is reached. Center: Pre-steady state plot for the same parameters, with the logarithmic gain shown in a black dashed line; a threshold is reached. Inset: Logarithmic gain calculated for each point in the linear abundance plot (not shown). Bottom: Free R abundance plot in log scale at different times. Shorter measurement times shift the threshold to lower k_R values, while it disappears as the system approaches steady state. **d.** Effect of α on thresholds and sensitivity. Top: Log-scale plot of free R abundance for different α values. When $\alpha = 0$ the threshold disappears. Bottom: Logarithmic gain (G) for the curve corresponding curves. The most noticeable effect is the displacement of the threshold along the x-axis, rather than a change in the value of maximum G , the only exception being when $\alpha = 0$.

Figure 2. Ultrasensitivity and frequency decoding. **a.** miRNA-target reactions with a time-dependent miRNA transcription rate $k_M(t)$. **b.** Upper: miRNA synthesis rate consists of square pulses with frequency f and amplitude k_M^A oscillating around a mean k_M^m . Lower: mRNA target (R) time courses for unregulated (R_{basal}), oscillatory miRNA regulation (R_{pulse}), and constant miRNA regulation (R_{cons}). τ denotes the steady-state timescale under constant input. **c.** Equilibration times τ^{\nearrow} and τ^{\searrow} following increases or decreases in the miRNA synthesis rate between $k_M^m \pm k_M^A/2$, computed across different values of k_M^m and catalyticities (α). Parameters: $k_M^A = 5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ nM min}^{-1}$, $k_R = 4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ nM min}^{-1}$, $g_R = 2.4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$, $g_S = 4.8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$, $\beta = 1$, $\kappa^+ = 28.8 \text{ nM}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$, $\kappa^- = 0.12 \text{ min}^{-1}$, and $\gamma = 0.06456 \text{ min}^{-1}$. **d.** Fold repression (FR) vs frequency. FR is computed over the same timespan τ , ensuring an integer number of pulses. The dashed line indicates FR under constant miRNA regulation. Schematic representation of frequency-response metrics: advantage A , selectivity S , and preferred frequency f^* .

e. Schematic representation of frequency-response metrics: advantage A , selectivity S , preferred frequency f^* . **f.** Normalized metrics as a function of k_M^m : logarithmic gain (G) between the input k_M^m and the output R at steady state, normalized by its minimum value, and the frequency dependent metrics, A and S , normalized by their maxima. For a fixed amplitude k_M^A , each k_M^m defines the time window and frequency range used to compute FR_{cons} and $FR_{pulse}(f)$, from which A and S are derived. Parameters as in (c) except for $\beta = 0.8364$. **g.** Steady state target concentration R vs k_M^m for different catalyticities (α). Each point corresponds to a different parameter set. For each case, frequency-response metrics are computed from FR curves. Colorbars indicate the different metrics to quantify the frequency response: A (left), S (center) and f^* (right). Parameters as in panel (d).

Figure 3. miRNA-mediated noise modulation, bimodalities and cell states. **a.** Schema of an mRNA interacting with a miRNA for three different interaction strengths, highlighted by the thickness of the connecting links (greater the interaction strength, thicker the link). **b.** Mean level (continuous lines) and relative noise in terms of Coefficient of Variation, CV (dashed lines), of an mRNA species as a function of its transcription rate k_R for a system with one mRNA interacting with one miRNAs (as depicted in Figure 1a), following the color code of panel (a). As k_R increases, the mean value of R not bound in complex with miRNA $\langle R \rangle$ increases linearly above the threshold for high miRNA-target interaction strength (turquoise line), or increases in a nonlinear way if the interaction is lower (light blue and gray lines). The mRNA CV , CV_R , measured as the ratio between R 's standard deviation and its mean, decreases when increasing k_R , with a local maximum in proximity to the threshold if the miRNA-target interaction strength is high (turquoise dashed line). Globally, the mRNA CV increases when increasing the miRNA-target interaction strengths. **c.** Distributions of the free amount of mRNA R for three different values of k_R , highlighted in different red tones following the color code of dashed lines in panel (b) for the case with highest interaction strength (turquoise lines). In proximity to the k_R threshold value, the distribution is bimodal. **d.** Schema of a network of M miRNAs interacting with N mRNAs. The thickness of the connecting links represent the strength of the miRNA-mRNA interactions. **e.** Mean values of the different mRNAs schematized in panel (d) as function of mRNA R_1 transcription rate, k_R^1 . Since the different mRNAs are coupled through the miRNAs, each of them responds to changing in k_R^1 . The response is determined by the strength of the miRNA-mediated interactions connecting that specific mRNA to R_1 . **f.** Distributions of the different mRNAs schematized in panel (d) for a specific value of R_1 transcription rate k_R^1 (gray dashed line in panel (e)). Close to the threshold, multiple mRNAs can have bimodal distributions. **g.** Cartoons of the joint distribution of R_1 and R_2 , and of R_1 and R_n , where each dot represents a single cell and x-y coordinates are R_1 and R_2 (or R_1 and R_n) expression values. Gray shaded regions identify different cell clusters, or cell states.